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Innovation engineering project in collaboration of three international universities

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ABSTRACT

Innovations are a prerequisite for enterprises in order to be successful and competitive in fastly developing markets demanding interdisciplinary development of complex products. The education of engineers in universities has to enable them to deal with these challenges and growing international cooperation in most business areas.

A consortium of three universities of applied sciences (UAS) from Finland, the Netherlands and Germany has agreed to advance their curricula by these demands and to set up an international collaboration of a group of universities and companies to educate students in projects that teach them how to develop innovation in collaboration with companies.

This paper describes theoretical background, the setup and the planning process of this project.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Curriculum Development, Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning

Keywords: *Project Learning, Design Education, Interpersonal skills, International Collaboration,*

1 INTRODUCTION

Actual and future markets in a globalized world challenging companies in all fields of technology are developing their portfolio fastly. Therefore innovations (= new and economically successful products [1]) are a prerequisite for enterprises in order to be successful and competitive in these markets. Furthermore most products require the interdisciplinary combination of e.g. mechanical, electrical and software components. Companies not only have to know their area of expertise but also to be able to adopt quickly to a changing environment, open up new markets as intrapreneurs (= persons working within the company having entrepreneurial capabilities) and possibly developing lead innovations worldwide.

These tasks challenge the Innovative, Interdisciplinary, International, Intrapreneurial and Interpersonal (= i⁵) skills of engineers and universities of applied sciences have to be able to educate especially engineers to fulfil these requirements. Engineers have to be able to command the entire chain from the first idea up to the product in the market. This chain includes product development, production and marketing.

When observing the curricula of engineering education within Europe, it can be seen that this kind of skills hardly, or not in coherence to each other, is implemented. A consortium of universities of applied sciences (UAS) from Finland, the Netherlands and Germany has been setup to get more experiences implementing these aptitudes in their curricula. Starting graduates are being positioned in key roles in SMEs and there they can help Companies to develop meaningful innovations. UAS (universities of applied sciences) therefore need to decide to adopt in their curricula i⁵-competencies to these needs and to set up an international collaboration of a group of universities and companies to educate students in projects that teach them how to develop innovation in collaboration with companies.

The basic idea is to set up a mixed group of students from all three UAS, give them an innovative development task from a company. This is important especially in the case when the graduated engineer is employed in a small and medium sized enterprise and in the case when the young engineer creates his/her own company. In bigger companies there is always need to find new managerial potential to be trained for higher management. The first implementation of the setup is planned in spring 2018.

This paper describes theoretical background, the setup and the planning process of international design projects in cooperation with companies, their allocation in the bachelor programs of mechanical engineering at the Universities of Applied Sciences in Oulu, Eindhoven and Ulm. Experiences in planning process and consequences will be drawn up for future education of engineers.

2 THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Outstanding Mechanical Engineers are essential for enterprises in order to develop new and successful products for actual and future markets. Thus universities all over the world are challenged by industry's demand for ideally ready-for-practice engineers coming out of study programmes and to orient their study programmes on the actual needs of industry in the area. Curricula have to be extended beyond deep knowledge of "the fundamentals" of professional engineering and the ability to apply it in practice that is taken for granted by most employers.

These requirements have also influenced accreditation criteria, thus study programs in mechanical engineering should ensure, that students “apply principles of engineering, basic science, and mathematics ...; to model, analyze, design, and realize physical systems, components or processes; and prepare students to work professionally in either thermal or mechanical systems while requiring topics in each area” [2].

After finishing mechanical engineering programs, students must be able to work professionally in an engineering environment and to “identify, formulate and solve engineering problems” under typical boundary conditions and to apply and extend their knowledge independently [2].

To fulfil these criteria, professional engineers ideally should have an “entrepreneurial” spirit and some skills beyond pure technical knowledge, here described as the i^5 skills based on Geraedts [3], Fig. 1. The authors therefore aim at integrating these skills into their study programs.

Fig. 1. i^5 – Approach [3]

- The development of **innovative** products deserves that mechanical engineers must acquire basic knowledge about patents as well as methodological approaches in developing innovative products. The importance of these abilities is stressed intensively in literature [4], [5], [6]. This ability is strengthened by project tasks that are based on largely untackled problems taken out of the “real world”.
- Entrepreneurship is important both for the development of national economies and for career of young engineers. Entrepreneurial thinking is not only important for founding new companies but also for the long-term development of existing companies, here called "**Intrapreneurship**". Nevertheless, entrepreneurship as “process of transmitting entrepreneurial knowledge and skills to students to help them exploit a business opportunity” [7] it is rather rarely taught in engineering programs. There are approaches to add this knowledge by extra-curricular activities [8] Expanding lectures by teaching basic questions of company foundation, project tasks requesting parts of it like setting up a business plan, visiting fairs, presenting ideas to potential sponsors or even providing a business

- incubator as a university are possible targets of projects in engineering programs.
- **Interpersonal** skills include advanced knowledge about communication within teams, companies or towards customers and public, team leadership and other skills needed for successful implementation of complex projects [9]. Engineers have to be able to arrange duties and to ensure their performance, to create an open minded atmosphere within the teams, to recognise and improve their strengths and weaknesses and to cope with conflicts. Methodical competences particularly include the ability to recognise and analyse technical problems, to plan a way to solve problems, find an adequate solution and to reflect the chosen approach critically. They can be encouraged by setting up a realistic and challenging environment for student projects e.g. in cooperation with companies.
 - Modern technologies are typically **interdisciplinary** and involve the combination of knowledge and technologies from diverse disciplines. Engineers must be able to determine the interfaces between their area of expertise and other disciplines and to define these interfaces, their interdependencies and their mutual requirements. Therefore they must have a basic knowledge of neighbouring disciplines, to be able to understand project partners from other disciplines and to communicate successfully with each other. Project tasks for mechanical engineering students should include aspects of other disciplines like economy, software engineering, electronics or even ethical or social disciplines.
 - In an increasingly globalized economic world engineers need **international** experiences to be able to communicate with customers and project partners all over the world. This requires not only to improve language skills but also to support students in gathering intercultural knowledge and the ability to cooperate in international teams or internationally distributed projects. The most effective way of obtain this experience is working in foreign countries, which is difficult to generally integrate into study programmes. Alternatively an increasing number of universities launch “internationalization at home” as a substitute by lecturing in foreign languages (preferably English), inviting guest teachers from foreign countries or involving international students in their study programs. The approach of the project described in this article is to or organize international projects in cooperation with partner universities or companies from other countries.

Based on these foundation, the partner universities decided to set up a collaborative student project that is targeting at teaching students the i⁵- skills.

3 OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

The collaborating universities started cooperating in exchange programs a couple of years ago and are regularly comparing their educational approaches and their study programs. They realised, that several objectives support the needs of all partner universities and partner countries. From the point of view of universities, goals are:

Educational objectives:

- Enhanced curricula with a focus on i⁵
- Implement innovation and entrepreneurship oriented education
- Evaluate new ways of teaching in universities
- Strengthened education oriented on the actual needs of industry in the area
- “Internationalisation at home” as an enabler for international experience for students

Collaborative objectives

- Increase the number of students and staff involved in international activities and mobilities
- Advance existing cooperations between universities, companies and institutions
- Improve the quality of international collaboration between universities and companies
- Demonstrate new ways of collaboration between companies and increase and internationalise cooperation with companies of different sectors and sizes
- Include company staff in international activities

Entrepreneurial objectives

- Encourage and enable students to innovate and achieve patentable ideas
- Encourage students to start entrepreneurial activities
- Strengthen intrapreneurial abilities of students and within universities

Industrial and organisation partners target at **collaborational objectives**

- Lower the barrier of SMEs to start collaboration with universities
- Start sustainable collaboration between universities and companies
- Aim at high quality of collaboration between companies and universities
- Build up international contacts and collaboration to universities and companies
- Support sustainable innovation activities in SMEs
- Support entrepreneurial companies in expanding their portfolio
- Strengthen intrapreneurial abilities within companies
- Recruitment of talented students
- Learn from quality-assured systematic innovation projects how to improve the development process within the company
- Facilitate innovative ideas for the development of the company
- Build up connection to universities and to expert knowledge
- Achieve patentable ideas and competitive advantages

Prior to this project, OUAS (Oulu University of Applied Sciences) and FUAS (Fontys University of Applied Sciences) have executed, just the two of them, several projects where students have searched for an idea, created a concept, realized the design and built the prototypes. The student groups have been a combination of students from both universities. In that project, the students have not made proper business scrutiny. In the project of this research, the idea is to widen the work to cover preparing to the production and marketing, as well. Also, the financing of the entire product process will be taken into account. The project group will not only be students from different universities, but from different disciplines as well. The guidance of the project will be performed by university teachers together with the professionals from businesses. In this way, students will reach a feeling of real business and entrepreneurship. Along the project, the students can experience the holistic chain from the search of an idea up to the market. They learn also how to work internationally. In this connection the communication in the working group and in meetings is one big subject and use of digital communication technology as well. It is not only technology they learn but also how to work professionally with people who have been educated in different countries in different sectors like in business and technology as well as in different methods. Because the length of the project will be three years, it is possible to follow the whole chain. After this kind of experience, students are more ready to take a responsible position in a company having own products. The position of product manager is especially suitable for an engineer possessing this kind of special education.

4 SETUP OF THE PROJECT

Based upon the objectives of the project, the project partners decided to set up a project-based learning environment to allow the successful integration of i^5 key competencies in undergraduate courses for engineering design students. The setup of the project is shown in Fig. 2.

The general aim of the project is to create a model to realize engineering and business education into the direction of innovations and entrepreneurship in technology sector together with enterprises. Thus each partner university cooperates with 2 companies to ensure close contact to industrial practice and a real entrepreneurial environment where students work in real development projects together with employees from businesses.

The main task of these participating industrial partners is to offer project ideas and to accompany the students during the solution phase to bring in a realistic environment. The project setup is completed by institutional partners like the chamber of commerce and a patent office to add information about the handling of innovations and chances of entrepreneurs.

Fig. 2. Project setup

The project is carried out in technically oriented study programs, but will involve business students in all universities as well. The students will be organised in groups of 12 students from all 3 countries (4 from each country) and therefore have to cooperate in an international environment and to handle distributed product development. Their task is to solve a problem from a basic idea of a solution to prototypes and if it comes up along the development process that the idea is on the way to real market the development work will be continued as far as it is possible in the time limits of a student project. The idea is to start shorter projects that can be

solved within one round of the project and more complex tasks that need to be handed over to other group(s) in following project rounds to complete it. An idea can be also students' own, so that they will be supported by an industrial partner and institutions to develop their idea towards a real market. It is one goal of the setup of three project rounds to find out what kind of framework is most valuable for the students.

The development projects start with kick-off-meeting of all students and representatives of companies and institutions in one of the partner countries. Students can choose an idea that will be formed to a concept that is worth to develop further. They can form their teams, clarify open questions, make up a time plan and share the tasks and then continue the design work in their home universities and continue a virtual collaboration using digital media.

It is planned to involve not only technical students, but also business students to develop a business model around the coming product, conduct a survey about the market situation, clarify economical demands or the profitability of the product. All the actions on the way from the idea to the market will be identified and evaluated from economical point of view. This examination supports the technical product development decisions as well. Additionally, the business students analyse different financing possibilities that are available to realize the total innovation process up to market. This total view teaches technical students to understand the economic framework of innovation and business students to understand the technical problems on the way from an idea to a product.

During the project students also gain experience in working in international multicultural groups by guidance of business professionals. The result of the development work will be presented and professionals make an evaluation on it. Performance of students will be assessed and grades will be given regarding these evaluation. Students will be asked to write learning diaries to collect their experiences and evaluations of learning during the project.

Teachers of universities and representatives of companies will make evaluation about the project from an educational point of view. This will help to improve the project setup after the first pilot phase. Based on that an improved model to realize the next student project PILOT 2 will be done. At the moment it is planned to carry out 3 pilot phases and then transfer the experiences into a final model to be used in continuous practice in the partner universities.

5 CONCLUSION

This contribution describes the idea, the theoretical background and the planning of an international and interdisciplinary educational development project carried out by 3 European universities. The main idea is to integrate students of universities from different countries and to give them an innovative development task provided by industrial partners to create a realistic environment. In the next step, the idea will be implemented and results will be presented in future conferences.

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